

Supplementary Information

Structure and function of the metagenomic plastic-degrading polyester hydrolase PHL7 bound to its product

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Supplementary Methods:

Classical Molecular Dynamics

Molecular dynamics (MD) simulations of PHL7 (PDB [7NEI](#)) were carried out using AMBER20 along with the ff19SB force field¹ for protein atoms and the GAFF force field² for the EMT ligand atoms. The protonation state of the residues at pH 8.0 was estimated using the H++ server³. Then, the MD system was solvated with TIP3P water molecules and neutralized with counterions in a truncated octahedral box of 1.3 nm of padding with periodic boundary conditions. The system was first minimized using the steepest descent method with position restraints applied on waters and ions, followed by a second minimization without any position restraints. The system was heated from 0 to 298 K for 75 ps at a constant volume using a Langevin thermostat at 1 fs time step, followed by equilibration of the solvent and ligand atoms, of each system for 2.5 ns at 298 K with a restraint weight of 10 kcal/mol/Å² on all protein atoms at the constant pressure of 1 bar using a Berendsen barostat and a 2 fs time step. Subsequently, a similar equilibration step was performed with restraints applied only on the protein backbone atoms (2.5 ns at 2fs time step and a restraint weight of 10 kcal/mol/Å²) before the whole system was equilibrated for 2.5 ns under the same temperature and pressure conditions without restraints. Production MD runs were carried out in four replicas for 100 ns each, using a timestep of 2 fs and the SHAKE⁴ algorithm to constrain all bonds involving hydrogens. The particle mesh Ewald method⁵ was used for long-range electrostatics, with a 10 Å cutoff for short-range electrostatics. The geometry of EMT was optimized with Gaussian 09 (Gaussian, Inc, Wallingford CT) on the B3LYP/6–31G** level of theory, and assignment of AMBER atom types and calculation of RESP charges were done with Antechamber⁶. Independent runs were ensured by using random seeds for initial velocities during the equilibration step. Replicas were checked for structural convergence using the overall backbone root-mean-square deviation (RMSD) relative to the first frame. RMSD and per-residue root mean square fluctuations (RMSF) were calculated using CPPTRAJ of AmberTools22⁷. Distance analysis was conducted using MDAnalysis⁸ and Matplotlib (Matplotlib: A 2D Graphics Environment | IEEE Journals & Magazine) to generate figures.

Autodock VINA

Control docking calculations were carried out following Engelberger et al.⁹ using AutoDock Vina^{10,11}. For all variants docking was performed inside a volume of 11 × 27 × 11 grid points (1Å spacing between grid points) that comprises both subsites I and II. We used the same starting structures that were employed for Rosetta docking. We added the polar hydrogens for the protein and parameterized the system with Gasteiger charges and atom types using prepare_receptor4.py and prepare_ligand4.py scripts from MGLtools 1.5.7.

DiffDock

The DiffDock¹² machine learning model was used to predict the binding mode of a pentamer of PET. To generate the prediction we used as input the following smiles string:

Supplementary Tables:

Supplementary Table 1: Overview of point mutations introduced into PHL7.

position	functional location	target AA	reference protein	reference	G-PET weight loss (%) ¹			$\Delta T_m \pm SD$ (rel. to WT PHL7)
					4 h	8 h	16 h	
- (WT)	-	-	-	-	18.5 ± 1.00	40.8 ± 6.10	90.1 ± 2.78	0.00 ± 0.05
S131	catalytic nucleophile	A	-	-	n.d. ²	n.d.	n.d.	-0.63 ± 0.04
F63	subsite I	Y	<i>IsPETase</i> , LCC	16,17	18.4 ± 0.75	29.0 ± 0.71	83.0 ± 0.92	0.56 ± 0.04
		A	<i>IsPETase</i> , LCC	16,17	3.0 ± 0.16	6.7 ± 0.16	10.8 ± 0.12	0.07 ± 0.05
M132	subsite I	W	PHL4	14	n.d.	n.d.	2.9 ± 0.38 (24 h)	1.98 ± 0.17
L93	subsite I	F	LCC	17	22.7 ± 0.89	50.2 ± 1.64	97.6 ± 2.00	1.19 ± 0.04
		A	-	-	19.7 ± 0.58	45.4 ± 0.78	92.0 ± 2.17	-0.44 ± 0.04
Q95	subsite I	Y	LCC	17	21.4 ± 0.68	48.4 ± 0.37	94.6 ± 3.38	0.80 ± 0.05
		G	LCC ICCG	17	16.4 ± 1.34	41.3 ± 1.03	67.7 ± 2.38	1.99 ± 0.04
H185	subsite I	S	<i>IsPETase</i>	18	4.0 ± 0.16	7.3 ± 0.36	10.0 ± 0.31	-11.52 ± 0.05
F189	subsite I	I	<i>IsPETase</i>	18	10.8 ± 0.49	14.7 ± 0.34	14.7 ± 1.35	-7.10 ± 0.07
H130	subsite IIa	W	<i>IsPETase</i> , PHL4-6	14,18	4.8 ± 0.28	8.1 ± 0.05	12.1 ± 0.18	-4.40 ± 0.07
L210	subsite IIa	F	LCC, <i>TfCut2</i>	17,19	12.9 ± 0.47	28.0 ± 0.65	55.9 ± 2.16	3.05 ± 0.03
		I	LCC ICCG	17	25.0 ± 0.13	52.9 ± 1.48	99.8 ± 0.33	-0.51 ± 0.06
		A	<i>IsPETase</i> , S238A	16,20	23.5 ± 0.94	52.5 ± 1.31	98.0 ± 2.00	0.37 ± 0.02
		S	<i>IsPETase</i>	16	20.8 ± 1.16	46.1 ± 1.57	92.7 ± 3.34	0.91 ± 0.05
		V	-	-	25.6 ± 0.58	54.3 ± 1.33	100	-0.21 ± 0.11
		T	-	-	26.3 ± 0.74	57.2 ± 1.54	100	1.36 ± 0.05
D233	metal binding site	K	-	-	25.4 ± 4.25	44.7 ± 6.02	97.6 ± 4.17	0.91 ± 0.10

¹: All weight loss experiments were conducted at 70 °C, mean values ± SD for n=3 experiments are shown.

²: No weight loss was detectable after 24 h.

Supplementary Table 2: Data collection and refinement statistics of the PHL7×TPA and PHL7×Mg²⁺ crystal structures.

	PHL7×TPA	PHL7×Mg ²⁺
Data collection		
Resolution range [Å]	21.57 - 1.7 (1.761 - 1.7) ¹	21.46 - 1.7 (1.761 - 1.7) ¹
Space group	P2 ₁	P2 ₁
Wavelength [Å]	1.5406	1.5406
Temperature [K]	100	100
Unit cell dimensions a, b, c [Å]	52.91, 56.51, 101.74	52.35, 56.07, 100.44
β [°]	94.11	94.01
Reflections	430,814 (32,577)	312,141 (21,198)
Unique reflections	66,097 (6,614)	63,959 (6,341)
Multiplicity	6.5 (4.9)	4.9 (3.3)
Completeness (%)	99.84 (99.97)	99.77 (99.83)
I/σ(I)	18.33 (2.80)	19.81 (3.02)
R _{merge}	0.07515 (0.4792)	0.05707 (0.3389)
R _{pim}	0.0303 (0.2392)	0.02696 (0.2168)
CC _{1/2}	0.998 (0.832)	0.997 (0.838)
Wilson B-factor	13.42	11.93
Refinement		
Reflections used in refinement	66,048 (6,612)	63,957 (6,341)
Reflections used for R _{free}	2,978 (323)	2,885 (319)
R _{work}	0.1600 (0.1972)	0.1296 (0.1723)
R _{free}	0.2059 (0.2495)	0.1604 (0.2103)
No. of non-hydrogen atoms:		
Protein	4,978	4,852
Solvent	4,036	4,006
Ligands	910	832
Ligands	56	20
RMS deviations		
Bonds [Å]	0.004	0.008
Angles [°]	0.77	0.96
Ramachandran		
Favored [%]	98.05	98.25
Allowed [%]	1.95	1.75
Outliers [%]	0.00	0.00
Molprobrity clashscore	2.74	1.39
Average B-factor		
Protein	18.27	16.60
Solvent	15.49	13.51
Ligands	30.35	31.32
Ligands	25.35	27.62
No. of TLS groups	2	2
PDB ID	8BRB	8BRA

¹: Values for highest resolution shell in parentheses.

Supplementary Table 3. Rank and score of Autodock Vina predictions and RMSD to the Rosetta predicted structure for each variant.

Variant	AutodockVina Prediction Rank	Autodock Score	RMSD to Rosetta [Å]
L210A	8	-5.1	2.279
L210F	2	-6.7	2.667
L210I	5	-5.1	2.780
L210S	5	-6.3	2.343
L210T	4	-5	2.556
L210V	5	-4.9	2.944
WT	4	-5	2.773

Supplementary Table 4. Score of Autodock Vina for the nine docking structures predicted for each variant. The structure that most closely resembles the Rosetta prediction is marked in yellow.

Variant	Autodock Prediction #	Autodock Score
L210A	1	-5.7
L210A	2	-5.5
L210A	3	-5.4
L210A	4	-5.3
L210A	5	-5.1
L210A	6	-5.1
L210A	7	-5.1
L210A	8	-5.1
L210A	9	-5
L210F	1	-6.8
L210F	2	-6.7
L210F	3	-6.7
L210F	4	-6.6
L210F	5	-6.5
L210F	6	-6.4
L210F	7	-6.4
L210F	8	-6.3
L210F	9	-6.3
L210I	1	-5.4
L210I	2	-5.3
L210I	3	-5.2
L210I	4	-5.2
L210I	5	-5.1
L210I	6	-5.1
L210I	7	-5.1

L210I	8	-5
L210I	9	-5
L210S	1	-6.4
L210S	2	-6.4
L210S	3	-6.4
L210S	4	-6.3
L210S	5	-6.3
L210S	6	-6.2
L210S	7	-6.2
L210S	8	-6.2
L210S	9	-6.2
L210T	1	-5.5
L210T	2	-5.1
L210T	3	-5
L210T	4	-5
L210T	5	-5
L210T	6	-4.9
L210T	7	-4.8
L210T	8	-4.7
L210T	9	-4.7
L210V	1	-5.3
L210V	2	-4.9
L210V	3	-4.9
L210V	4	-4.9
L210V	5	-4.9
L210V	6	-4.9
L210V	7	-4.8
L210V	8	-4.8
L210V	9	-4.6
WT	1	-5.2
WT	2	-5.1
WT	3	-5
WT	4	-5
WT	5	-5
WT	6	-5
WT	7	-5
WT	8	-4.8
WT	9	-4.8

Supplementary Figures:

PHL7	-----MANPYERGPDPTESSIEAVRGPFAVA	26
PHL4	-----MENPYERGPDPPTQSVEAARGPYAVS	26
LCC	MDGVLWRVRTAALMAALLALAALVWASPSVEAQSNPYQRGNPTRSALTADG-PFSVA	59
TfCut2	-----ANPYERGNPTDALLEARSGPFVS	25
IsPETase	-----MNFPRASRLMQAAVLGGLMAVSAATAQTNPYARGPNPTAASLEASAGPFTVR	53
	*** **:* * : * **:	
PHL7	QTTVSRQLQADGFGGGTIYYPTDTSQGTFGAVAI SPGFTAGQESIAWLGPRIASQGFVVIT	86
PHL4	QITVG-GQFGSYSGGTIYYPTSTADGKFGAVAIAPGFLSFQSSVAWLGPRIASQGFVVMT	85
LCC	TYTVSRLSVSGFGGGVIYYPTG-TSLTFGGIAMS PGYTADASSLAWLGRRLASHGFVVLV	118
TfCut2	EENVSRLSASGFGGGTIYYPR--ENNTYGAVAISP GYTGEASIAWLGERIASHGFVVIT	83
IsPETase	SFTVS--RPSGYGAGTVYYPTN-AGGTVGAIAIVPGYTARQSSIKWWGPRLASHGFVVIT	110
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PHL7	IDTITRLDQPSRGRQLQAALDHLRTN----SVVRNRIDPNRMVMGHSMGGGALSAA	141
PHL4	IDTGTIFDQPAQRGDQLLDALDFLTQR----SSVKDRIDPNRLAVAGWSMGGGSLEAA	140
LCC	INTNSRFLDQPSRASQLSALNYLRTSS--PSAVRARLDANRLAVAGWSMGGGTLRIA	175
TfCut2	IDTITRLDQPSRAEQLNALNHMINRA---SSTVRSRIDSSRLAVMGHSMGGGSLRLA	140
IsPETase	IDTNSTLDQPSRSSQMAALRQVASLNGTSSSPIYGVDTARMGMVGHSMGGGSLISA	170
	* : * : * * . * * * : * : * : * . * : * * * * * : * * * * *	
PHL7	ANNTSLEAAIPLQGWHTRKNWSSVRTPTLVVGAQLDTIAPVSSHSEAFYNSLPSDLKAY	201
PHL4	ADRPSLKAAPMAGWNLNTNWSRLTTPVLVVGVDLTIAPVAMHSEFFYNSIRS--EKAY	198
LCC	EQNPSLKAAPLTPWHTDKTFN-TSVPVLIVGAEADTVAPVSHAIFPYQNLPSSTPKVY	234
TfCut2	SQRPLKAAIPLTPWHLNKNWSSVTVPTLIIGADLDTIAPVATHAKFFYNSLPSSISKAY	200
IsPETase	ANNPSLKAAPQAPWDSSTNFSSVTVPTLIFACENDSIAPVNSALPTIYDSMSRN-AKQF	229
	: . . . : * * * * . * . . . : * : * * * : : . : * : *	
PHL7	MELRGASHIVSNTPD---TTTAKYSIAWLKRFVDDDLRYEQFLCPAP-DDFAISEYRSTCPF--	259
PHL4	LELAGGSHFTVTSAN---TPQAKLMI SWLKRFVNDTRYEQFICPGPSRGFSVSEYRSTCPY--	257
LCC	VELDNASHFAPNSNN---AAISVYTI SWMLWVDNDTRYRQFLCNVNDPALSDFRNTNHRHC--	293
TfCut2	LELDGATHFAPNIPN---KII GKYSVAWLKRFVNDTRYTQFLCPGPRDGLFGEVEEYRSTCPF	261
IsPETase	LEINGGSHSCANGSNQALIGKKGVAWMKRFMDNDTRYSTFACENPNSTRVSDFRNTANCS---	290
	: * : . . : * : * : * * : * : * * * * *	

Supplementary Figure 1: Overview of the sites mutated in this study and origin of the chosen replacement residues. A multiple sequence alignment shows the corresponding positions (boxed) selected for mutagenesis and the amino acids to which those positions were mutated (filled residues). The catalytic triad is shown in red, subsite I in blue, subsite II in green (PHL7 residue numbering). A structural overview of the binding site with the docking model for EMT generated in this study (dark grey) is shown below. Mutation sites are underlined. Superposition of the TPA ligand (yellow) derived from the PHL7×TPA crystal structure (PDB:[8BRB](#)) confirms a productive conformation of the docked EMT molecule.

Supplementary Figure 1: Binding of TPA and DMSO to subsite I of PHL7. **a** T178 of chain B (dark blue) interacts with the distal carboxyl group of TPA (grey, distance in Å). **b** Superimposition of the two individual PHL7 chains A (light blue) and B (dark blue) of the PHL7×TPA cocrystal structure. Both the residues as well as the ligands TPA and DMSO (chain A: light grey, chain B: dark grey) align well. Therefore, interaction of T178 of chain B with TPA of chain A does not influence the conformation of the active site.

Supplementary Figure 2: Superimposition of subsite I of PHL7×TPA (light blue) and apo PHL7 (light green, PDB ID: [7NEI](#)). Binding of TPA does not significantly alter the conformation of binding residues.

Supplementary Figure 3: Comparison of the subsite I architecture between PHL7, LCC and *IsPETase*. **a** Superimposition of subsite I of PHL7×TPA (light blue, TPA in grey) with apo structures of the homologous polyester hydrolases LCC (blue, PDB ID: [4EB0](#)), *IsPETase* (salmon, PDB ID: [5XJH](#)) and *TfCut2* (green, [4CG1](#)). The conformations of structurally equivalent residues are well conserved among these enzymes. *IsPETase* as a mesophilic polyester hydrolase deviates most significantly from the other enzymes that all belong to the thermophilic group. The residues of PHL7 are labeled accordingly. **b** Superimposition of PHL7×TPA (light blue, TPA in dark grey) and *IsPETase* (PDB ID: [5XGO](#), thin sticks). W185 as part of the subsite I π -stacking clamp of *IsPETase* adopts three distinct conformations, one in each individual molecule of the asymmetric unit (chain A: salmon; B: light green; C: blue), accompanied by different conformations of the neighboring S214. This conformational flexibility is restricted for the structurally equivalent W156 of PHL7 due to the neighboring H185. PHL7 W156 adopts a conformation most similar to conformation C of *IsPETase*. Exchange of H185S in PHL7 decreases both thermal stability and PET degradation activity.

Supplementary Figure 5: Magnesium binding site of PHL7×Mg²⁺. The carboxylic sidechain of D246 and five water molecules complex a Mg²⁺ ion in the first interaction sphere. Three of the five water molecules in

turn interact with the carboxylic sidechains of E13, D246 and D247, respectively. The binding site is ~ 28 Å away from the active site. All distances in Å.

Supplementary Figure 6: Inhibition effect of MHET on PHL7 WT **a** and variant L210F **b**. The reaction rate is specified as reduction of the apparent film thickness per hour, which was measured by impedance spectroscopy¹⁵. An inverse Michaelis-Menten kinetic experiment was performed ranging from enzyme concentrations of 6.8 to 111 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ and an inhibitor concentration of 20 mM MHET was tested. **c:** Calculated $\text{Inv}K_m$ and V_{max} values for the WT and variant L210F with 0 and 20 mM MHET. $\text{Inv}K_m$ describes the enzyme concentration at half-maximum reaction velocity. Mean values for $n=3$ replicates \pm SD are shown.

Supplementary Figure 7: Single mutants sorted by their melting point and their hydrolytic PET weight loss activity relative to PHL7 WT (black square). The triangles are color-coded (T_m decrease in blue, increase in red) and point upwards (increased weight loss activity) or downwards (decreased activity). The enzyme variants comprise three distinct classes: 1) drastically decreased activity and retained or decreased thermal stability (blue area), 2) increased thermal stability with varying activity (green) and 3) increased activity while maintaining or increasing thermal stability (red). Especially the red-green overlapping region contains double-gain variants interesting for further protein engineering. The optimal reaction temperature of 70 °C (which also resembles T_g of PET) is depicted with a dashed line.

Supplementary Figure 8: Results of AutodockVina control docking calculations. Panel **a, c, e, g, i,** and **k** correspond to L210A, L210I, L210F, L210S, L210T, L210V, and WT, respectively. The EMT ligand lowest energy structure of Rosetta's most populated cluster is depicted in purple sticks. Shown in orange is Autodock's structurally closest prediction to Rosetta. As a comparison on the right column, panel **b, d, f, h, j, l,** and **n** correspond to an overlay of the nine predicted poses created with Autodock Vina.

Supplementary Figure 9: Overview of the largest molecule clusters of the 50 best energy docking models of EMT for each L210X variant tested. The model with the most likely lowest energy binding mode was selected from the largest model cluster, which is displayed on the left-hand column and contained 60-76% of the top 50 docking poses (from 40'000 generated poses in total). The Rosetta interface_delta_X score was used to estimate the energy of interaction. At the same time, each most populated cluster was aligned with the TPA crystallographic structure ([8BRB](#)) to confirm that its terephthalic ring resembled the same orientation and position. Furthermore, it is important to note that our method was able to identify alternative binding modes that have lower abundance but slightly better interface_delta_X scores in some cases (e.g. cluster #3 WT).

Supplementary Figure 10. Docking poses of EMT in PHL7 overlaid with the crystallized TPA molecule in PHL7. Aromatic rings of EMT molecules (gray sticks) from cluster #1 superimpose clearly with the aromatic ring of TPA (yellow sticks) bound to the crystal structure of PHL7×TPA ([8BRB](#)).

A

Supplementary Figure 11. MD simulation results for PHL7-EMT docking model. **a** Distance between the oxygens of the EMT molecule and the γ -oxygen of the catalytic serine (S131) over the simulation time (100 ns) for each L210X variant and the WT. For every 100 frames of the simulation the mean distance and SD were calculated. The distance considered as catalytically competent (2.5 - 5 Å) is marked as a light orange band. The S131 γ -oxygen is hydrogen-bonded with at least one oxygen of EMT over the entire time course in every MD simulation, except in two replicates for L210F and one replicate for L210V. RESP: restrained electrostatic potential. **b** Representation of the EMT ligand, with the oxygen atoms marked in the same colors as in (A) and labeled with their respective names. The oxygen atoms involved in forming the ester bonds are O1, O2 and O8.

Supplementary Figure 12. Predicted binding mode of PHL7 with 2-HE(MHET)₄ generated using the DiffDock deep learning model. PHL7 is represented as surface model and the catalytic triad (red), subsite I (blue) and subsite II (green) are colored. The 2-HE(MHET)₄ is represented as sticks and sphere model. Residues of the ligand that are expected to interact with the enzyme are colored according to the respective subsite. **a** A binding mode is proposed for the 2-hydroxyethyl-(monohydroxyethyl terephthalate)₄, (2-HE(MHET)₄) ligand. **b** The proposed product after catalytic cleavage and a depiction of the hypothesized relative movement of the PET chains (indicated by black arrows) are shown.

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